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RETAILERS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS REGIONAL BRANDS' DETERGENT PRODUCTS

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Abstract

In today's situation, every one of us is concentrating more on health aspects and prefers the most hygienic and unharmed products. Usage of best detergents is the identification of seeking fundamental health. I carried out a study on "Retailers' perception towards the regional brands' detergent products" in 4 districts of Ramnad, Pudukottai, Sivaganga, and Dindugal. As the population of the retailers is unknown, 154 retailers are considered as the respondents. They have been surveyed with the help of a structured questionnaire to understand the movement pattern of the detergent products of regional brands, their influencing factors on product, price, place, and promotions along with their overall satisfaction towards the regional brands. The data collected has been surveyed and involved in percentage analyses for all the multiple-choice questions and mean for the 5-point rating scale questions. I hope this research will help regional brands of detergent products to identify their best and where to concentrate more to improve further.

Introduction

Detergent products are used for the purpose of killing germs in clothes and household products. In the earlier stages of the sixteen to the eighteenth century, manufacturing factories in Italy and France were using Olive oil as the basic essential ingredient to produce soaps. In the year of 1882, Protector and Gamble in the US established the very first famous soap named "Ivory soap. In 1939, the costliest substance was produced in the name of alkylbenzene sulfonate (ABS) which resulted in better cleaning process rather than others.

Lever brothers introduced modern soaps into the Indian market through importing. The first Indian soap manufacturing company is The North-West Soap Company. Mr. Jamshedji Tata initiated his soap manufacturing unit and branded their soap in the 1930s "The Tata Oil Mills Company". The data insist that around 70% of the Indian population are residing in rural areas. So that 50% of the soaps were sold in rural areas only. In the 1960s Hindustan Lever Limited started to establish itself in this business. Today several brands of toiletry soap companies are emerging by value additions to their products and striving hard to position them in different varieties.

A normal person of a rural background spends 5% of their income on detergents. So small entrepreneurs and start-ups are focusing on their regional segment to position their brands among them. It is important to know the retailers' perception and their satisfaction, as they are the persons who sell their market in the market, and they are the middlemen between the manufacturers and the customers. By the way, this research can be able to fulfill the needs and wants of the end consumers.

Review of literature

P. Indira Gandhi and Dr. S. Adaikala Charles (2018) conveyed that introduction of premium products in sachet helps the rural people to experience their quality and found that those people are preferring detergents to the fabric washer.

Ahuja and Sharma (2018) concluded that the people who are young, and literal prefers the costliest and most branded detergent products. Sahsham Rawat (2017) said that people are considering that the formation of more foam ensures the efficient cleaning of clothes.

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Ada Ferri et.al (2016) researched that the occurrence of damage in clothes is not because of the quality of detergents alone but also with some other factors.

Alaka and Subhra (2015) determined that the consumers are establishing low involvement purchase behavior and they weren't ensuring that they will sustain as a long-term brand loyal customer.

R. Shanthaseela and Dr. V. Saravanan (2015) analyzed that HUL has obtained the huge market share and suggested improvising the promotional activities of different brands as there is a chance for the introduction of several detergent brands. International journal of Advancements in research and technology (2013) suggested that the branded product which has better quality with a reasonable price have tremendous opportunities as the consumers prefer the products based on their brand name, quality, and their pricing strategies.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the movement pattern of regional brands' detergent products.
2. To know the retailers' perception towards regional brands' detergent products.
3. To find the retailers' rank for their overall satisfaction towards regional brands' detergent products.

Methodology

This research is in the form of a descriptive study where the primary data is collected from the retailers. The data was collected using a direct survey method. The respondents are the retailers of the detergent brands from the districts of Ramnad, Pudhukottai, Sivaganga, and Dindugal in Tamil Nadu state. The data was collected through the personal interview from 10.3.2022 to 10.04.2022. The population size is unknown, and the sample size is 154 retailers. A convenience sampling method was used and administered through a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire contains multiple-choice questions, 5-point rating scale questions and a ranking question. The research is analyzed with the help of percentage analysis, pie chart, mean, and chi-square test.

Results and discussions

Profile of the respondents

Table 1- Respondents' districts

Distribution of Respondents	Respondents' characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
District	Ramnad	74	48.05 %
	Pudhukottai	4	2.60 %
	Sivaganga	22	14.29 %
	Dindugal	54	35.06 %

Table 1 shows that the respondents from various mentioned districts are classified as above i.e., 48.05 % from Ramnad, 35.06 % from Dindugal, 14.29 % from Sivaganga and 2.60 % from Pudhukottai.

Table 2- Type of the shop

Distribution of Respondents	Respondents' characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Type of the shop	Petty shop	23	14.94 %
	Grocery shop	90	58.44 %
	Departmental store	41	26.62 %

Table 2 shows that among these retailers, 58.44 % are dealing the products in grocery shops, 26.62 % are having departmental stores and 14.94 % are owning petty shops

Table 3- Location

Distribution of Respondents	Respondents' characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Location	Rural	70	45.45 %
	Semiurban	36	23.39 %
	Urban	48	31.16 %

Table 3 shows that these retailers' shops are in rural areas of about 45.45%, 31.16 % are in urban areas and 23.39 % in semiurban areas.

Table 4 - Number of years dealing with regional brands

Distribution of Respondents	Respondents' characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Number of years dealing with the regional brands	1 year	0	0 %
	2-5 years	5	3.24 %
	6-10 years	102	66.25 %
	Above 10 years	47	30.51 %

Table 4 shows that at the maximum, 66.25 % are dealing for around 6-10 years, 30.51 are dealing for more than 10 years and 3.24 % of retailers are dealing with regional brands for about 2-5 years.

Movement pattern

Table 5

Distribution of respondents	Respondents' characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Regional brands' detergent products in retailers' shop	Detergent cakes	152	98.70 %
	Detergent powder	40	25.9 %
	Liquid detergent	8	5.19 %
Fast-moving product	Detergent cake-125 gm	150	97.41 %
	Detergent cake-250 gm	4	2.59 %
Sales representative visit	Weekly	154	100 %
Promotional activity	Offers	154	100 %
Competitors for regional detergent brands	Power soaps	45	29.22 %
	Arasan soaps	60	38.96 %
	Rin soaps	4	2.59 %
	Oorvasi soaps	5	3.24 %
	Ponvandu soaps	37	24.05 %
	Others	3	1.94 %

Suitable media to increase sales	Television	119	77.27 %
	Social media	35	22.72 %

Table 5 shows about the movement pattern of regional brands' detergent products. Initially, it is observed that the number of retailers using the regional brands' detergent products in their shops. 98.70 % are having detergent cakes, 25.90 % are having detergent powder and 5.19 % are dealing with liquid detergent of regional brands. 97.14 % of retailers admitted that 125 gm detergent cakes are the fast-moving detergent product and 2.59 % revealed that 250 gm detergent cakes are the fast-moving products. 100 % of the retailers responded that the promotional activity the availed offers and their sales representatives visit their shops weekly once to replace their orders. The competitors for the regional brands of detergent products, 38.96 % of retailers said Arasan soaps, 29.22 % considered Power soaps, 24.05 % said that Ponvandu soaps as the competitors, 3.24 % said Oorvasi soaps, 2.59 % said Rin soaps and 1.94 % retailers picked the options others. 77.27 % of respondents said that television will be the most suitable media to increase the sales of regional brands of detergent cakes and 22.72 % of retailers consider social media as the correct media platform to increase the sales of these regional brands.

Retailers' payment preference

Table 6

Distribution of respondents	Respondents' characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Most preferred payment method	Cash	133	86.36 %
	Credit	21	13.64 %
	Cheque	0	0 %
	Online payment	0	0 %
Most preferred online payment mode	Gpay	92	59.74 %
	Phone pay	14	9.09 %
	Paytm	25	16.24 %
	Amazon pay	23	14.93 %
	Others	0	0 %

Table 6 shows that. 86.36 % of respondents are preferring cash as their most preferred payment method and the remaining 13.64 % of respondents are preferring credit. Among all the respondents, 59.54 % are preferring Gpay as the most preferred online payment mode, 16.24 % are preferring Paytm, 14.93 % are preferring Amazon pay and the remaining 9.09 % are preferring Phone pay for the online payment mode.

Retailers' perception towards the regional brands' detergent products

Table 7

Factors	Items	Mean
Product	Quality of the product is good	4.61
	Package design of the product is attractive	4.38
	Aroma of the product smells good	4.50
	Products are delivered without damages	4.65
	Return policies are easy	4.70

	Customers are satisfied with the quality of the goods	4.80
Price	The price of the product is reasonable	4.25
	Profit margin is high	3.94
	Satisfied with the company's offers and discounts	3.49
	Satisfied with the payment terms	3.96
Promotion	Distribution of free samples increases the credibility	4.18
	Satisfied with the advertisement	3.16
	Print media advertisements are up to the mark	3.46
Place	Frequency of salesperson visit is satisfied	4.72
	Products are delivered in time	4.81
	Required quantity of the products are delivered without delay	4.85

Table 7 shows that the retailers' perception was observed with the 5-point scale rating questions for the factors of product, price, promotion, and place. In this 5-point rating was structured as 5- strongly agree, 4- agree, 3- neutral, 2- Disagree and 1- strongly disagree. It is inferred that; the retailers are mostly agreeing with all the statements in product and place factors. It is found that in terms of price and promotional factors the regional brands must concentrate and improvise to increase the satisfaction level of their retailers who deal with their detergent products.

Retailers' overall satisfaction towards regional brands' detergent products

The retailers have ranked the regional brand detergent products for their overall satisfaction. This ranking question is structured from rank 1 and rank 5 where the rank 1 is the best and the rank 5 is the worst. 76.62 % of retailers have ranked at the second position, 22.72 % of retailers felt that these regional brands are at third rank in case of overall satisfaction and the remaining 0.64 % ranked at the first position whereas as 1 being the best and 5 is the worst.

Analyses of relationship among variables

A chi-square test was carried out to study the relationship between the independent variables and all dependent variables.

It is found that there is a significant relationship between the retailers' districts and the following factors,

1. Fast-moving product.
2. Competitors.
3. The price of the products is reasonable.
4. Profit margin is high.
5. Satisfied with the company's offers and discounts.
6. Distribution of free samples increases the credibility.

It is found that there is a significant relationship between the type of the shop and the following factors,

1. Competitors.
2. Most preferred payment method.
3. Distribution of free samples increases the credibility.
4. Frequency of salesperson visits.

It is also inferred that there is a significant relationship between the location of the shop and the following factors,

1. Fast-moving products.
2. The price of the product is reasonable.
3. Satisfied with the company's offers and discounts.
4. Satisfied with the payment terms.
5. Distribution of free samples increases the credibility.
6. Satisfied with the advertisements.
7. Print media advertisements are up to the mark.

It is observed that there is a significant relationship between the number of years dealing with regional brands' detergent products and the following factors,

1. Satisfied with the quality of products.
2. Return policies are easy.
3. Distribution of free samples increases the credibility.

Conclusion

It is inferred from the analyses that the regional brands are being best in the quality aspect from the retailers' perception, and they can improvise their promotional strategy to increase their sales further and can encourage online sales as of now, this generation people are mostly searching their needs and wants with the usage of internet. They can focus and increase their targeting segments. It is found that the regional brands have reached out and captured most of the rural areas by targeting their customers from the rural markets and they are providing their best. They satisfy their retailers by providing frequent offers and supplying their products without any complaints in regard to the products and provides the easy return policies too. As the majority of the retailers are dealing with for a decade, it assures that regional brands have loyal customers. The rank, they acquired from the retailers insists that regional brands are competing in a better way and are being the best in their targeted market.

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